

ADVANCING ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES VIA EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19084790>

Abstract

The focus of this investigation is to advance the plight of entrepreneurship education (EE) through the intelligence of entrepreneurship students. A descriptive survey design was adopted, leveraging a close-ended questionnaire to obtain adequate information from the respondents (male and female 300 and 400 levels entrepreneurship students in Ekiti State Tertiary Institutions). Multi-stage and simple random sampling techniques were employed to sample the higher institutions and the entrepreneurship students, respectively. Data was sourced from both secondary and primary data. The primary data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study reveals that emotional intelligence has more substantial efficacy on extracurricular activities within the spectrum of good sense of feelings, better understanding of self-emotions, self-feeling, and happy mood, among others. It is recommended that students possess more EI and SI for overall performance and managing themselves and others.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, social intelligence, entrepreneurship students, skewness, entrepreneurship education.*

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is crucial for nations' global competitiveness in the knowledge-based economy. It is widely recognised as a means to enhance economic growth, innovation, creativity and capacity development. There has been an increasing interest in founding educational programmes that Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK promote and improve entrepreneurship (Boldureanu, Alina, Bercu, Bedrule-grigorut & Boldureanu, 2020). Entrepreneurship education (EE) has gained significant attention in tertiary Institutions (Farny, Hannibal, Frederiksen & Jones, 2019) because of its capacity to link real-world business operations with theory. Similarly, there has been a rise in research interest in EE due to greater emphasis on teaching in this field (Ratten & Usmanij, 2020).

The policy has portrayed EE as a critical effort in enhancing, promoting and realising venture culture and the development of students for overall benefits (Farny et al., 2019). Given that education serves as a means for society to express its core ideals, the strategy aims to integrate Entrepreneurship Education (EE) into all levels of the curriculum and significantly expand the availability of university courses focused on entrepreneurship (Blenker, Frederiksen, Korsgaard, Muller, Neergaard and Thrane, 2012), just the way it has received rousing acceptance in the Nigerian educational space. The Romanian government introduced EE into the country's curriculum for secondary schools in 2002, this was extended to tertiary education in 2013 in alignment with the European Union's 2020 Entrepreneurship Action Plan (DG Enterprise and

Industry, 2020), it included the introduction of theoretical courses on entrepreneurship into the curricula for undergraduate and graduate students (Boldureanu, Alina, Bercu, Bedrule-grigorut and Boldureanu, 2020).

With effect from the 2007–2008 academic year, all Nigerian Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) students were required by the National Universities Commission to take EE as a required course in 2006 (Olorundare & Kayode, 2014). It was emphasised once more that, in reality, certain higher education institutions merely create one or two courses on entrepreneurship, with instructors instructing them who have no background in entrepreneurship (norm and certification) (Onuma, 2016; Tambari & Popnwin, 2017; Ugochukwu et al., 2016; Uzoagulu, 2012), this conforms with the position of (Aruleba, 2019). Out of their ingenuity and support from the relevant private and public establishment, initiatives launched in universities to spur students to begin start-ups include the construction of self-employment/career service, university seedbed development, or creative and entrepreneurship workshops (Barba-Sánchez & Atienza-Sahuquillo, 2016), of recent was the establishment of Skill and Enterprise Development Centre of the Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology (BOUESTI); while Ekiti State University Centre for Entrepreneurship; Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation, University of Ibadan; and the Enterprise Development Centre of the Pan Atlantic University and among others were created earlier in Nigeria.

Higher education institutions in Nigeria that offer instruction and learning beyond the upper secondary level include universities and interuniversity centres, polytechnics, colleges of education, mono-technics, and other specially founded colleges spread throughout the nation. EE Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK has the hallmark and capacity to develop students with strong skills, knowledge, and a focus on potentials (career exploration, financial skill, community awareness, good relationships, education, and business knowledge) capable of enhancing business and entrepreneurial potentials to rebuild their perception (Aruleba, 2019).

In 1920, Edward Thorndike distinguished intelligence into three categories: abstract, mechanical, and social: abstract denotes understanding and managing ideas; mechanical means understanding and managing concrete objects; and social means understanding and managing people and communities. Ordun, Özveren and Mercimek (2021), social intelligence is primarily associated with acting wisely in human connections. Emotional Intelligence (EI) has a role in self-regulation, which includes impulse control. For instance, the management of aggression and irresponsible behaviour (alcohol and drug abuse) is a function of emotional intelligence possessed by such individuals (García-Sancho, Salguero and Fernández-Berrocal, 2014; Kopera, Jakubczyk, Suszek, Glass, Klimkiewicz, Wnorowska, Brower & Wojnar, 2015).

Universally, humans are regarded as social entities. In this light, the social species that has the social identity can be his/her better version with the possession of social intelligence (SI). Social intelligence is the ability and social technique not only to get along with people but also to identify social problems, a tendency to stimuli from other group members, and understanding momentary attitudes and essential individual features to both familiar and strangers (Tamasila, Pavlov, Todorova, Taucean & Diaconescu, 2024).

Lau, (2016) states that SI is an essential ability and skill cogent with general opportunities, career opportunities, and progression, with a touch of complex skills. It has positive effects on personal well-being and collective economic success. The first distinction (personal) refers to what a person must comprehend and grow on his or her own, whereas the second (social) refers to what a person can develop through interactions with others. This differentiation can also be made in terms of personal and social abilities. Personal skills are mostly cognitive talents, such as reasoning and knowledge, while social skills (SSs) are interpersonal connections (Engelberg, 2015). Generally, SSs may be subdivided into three basic categories: personal qualities (emotional intelligence), interpersonal skills (social intelligence), and additional skills/knowledge.

Entrepreneurship can help with some core issues facing today's economies, like joblessness and sluggish economic growth. It answers issues brought on by the faster-paced, more turbulent social and economic transformation. The beneficiaries of EE now have access to the same opportunities that come with entrepreneurship. Not everyone can think or behave entrepreneurially, which is a drawback of entrepreneurship education, which is why this study is necessary despite its benefits. Research in general education is frequently appropriated and used in an entrepreneurial context by Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK the discipline of EE. Although this was helpful in the early phases of the research, it is now time to create a more unique body of knowledge in EE using distinct constructs. This will enable us to examine what makes entrepreneurship education unique in a more perceptive and thoughtful manner.

Therefore, it is recommended that EE programmes be developed in order to boost the pool of entrepreneurial talent, facilitate flawless relationship building, and foster positive relationships among students and others. The primary goal of exposing kids to EE is to encourage more entrepreneurship. EE has the advantage of being applicable in various situations and circumstances, but there are also present issues that must be resolved. Social psychology has been the foundation for a large portion of the research on entrepreneurship regarding attitudes, behaviours, actions, and beliefs while neglecting the competencies needed to build relationships and excel in academic and non-academic activities. Notably, this study seeks to investigate the advancement of entrepreneurship education through emotional and social intelligence. The research's broad objective is to investigate the advancement of entrepreneurship education through emotional intelligence and social intelligence in Ekiti State. Notably, it sought to:

- i. Determine the efficacy of emotional intelligence in promoting extracurricular activities among entrepreneurship students in Ekiti State.
- ii. Explore the influence of social intelligence in enhancing academic activities among entrepreneurship students in Ekiti State.

LITERATURE

The field of entrepreneurship has advanced educating students on how to launch a new venture, ascertaining its possibilities and starting digital businesses, as well as how to keep friendly relationships with others (Nowinski, Haddoud, Lancaric, Egerova & Czegledi, 2019), this is due to educational change toward experiential learning (Ferreira, Fayolle, Ratten and Raposo, 2018). This indicates that assisting students in acquiring particular information and abilities in an actual situation is essential to their overall

development as entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship, as it is pushed in schools, provides a realistic depiction of how the world functions while also recommending worthwhile behaviours and ways to live in it (Farny et al., 2019); the ability to relate with others irrespective of the mood is quite an important variables being considered in this study. Kruger, (2004) believe that before entrepreneurship was recognised and accepted as a legitimate academic subject, it went through four basic stages of development: the development of systematic theory, entrepreneurship as a career, authorisation and professional organisation and, professional culture. The four developmental phases of entrepreneurship into academic discourse Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK align with social and emotional intelligence usage in advancing entrepreneurship education and career paths.

The objective of EE in universities is to change students' attitudes, values, and self-perceptions so they can explore who they are within the parameters of quotients and become enterprising. As a result of this shift, there is a greater emphasis on the entrepreneur as a person, as seen by specific skills and behaviours like social and emotional intelligence that need to be developed and trained (Farny et al., 2019). Interactive learning connected to corporate and community projects defines EE (Ratten & Usmanij, 2020) as an experience-based learning approach linking the industry. Due to the dynamic nature of teaching methods and the growing use of social media in the classroom, entrepreneurship education frequently includes guest speakers and case studies (Chawinga, 2017). This denotes that it's critical to focus educational activities by creating pertinent courses grounded in research and integrated into practice.

EE aims to change students' perceptions about creative entrepreneurial practices and efforts to relate with enterprise stakeholders (Ratten & Usmanij, 2020). Focusing on entrepreneurial learning (affective, cognitive, and skill-based) outcomes such as soft skills of emotional and social intelligence to ascertain whether students' behaviour has been positively affected by the EE. Affective consequences are shifts in attitudes regarding the desire to launch a new business or participate in innovation within an existing one. Critical thinking that arises from new information is an element of cognitive outputs, which is essential in today's complicated business environment; this includes understanding and learning about the motivations for launching a business (Jones & Colwill, 2013). The tools required to become an entrepreneur are included in skill-based outcomes. An increasing number of digital tools are becoming essential for enterprise founders. Analysing cognitive and affective learning and conception techniques to measure entrepreneurship education's effectiveness education.

The term affective learning describes how an educational experience alters a person's feelings and perspectives; this could entail learning about the ups and downs of an entrepreneur. Acquiring a new skill set for application in an enterprise setting is the goal of cognitive learning (Koronios, Kriemadis, Dimitropoulos & Papadopoulos, 2019). Conception means people's perceptions of the entrepreneurship process, which may include the belief that it is an advantageous aspect of conducting business. In today's practices, each of these several methods for teaching entrepreneurship is significant; more integration of an anthroposophic perspective on education is required in entrepreneurial education. An anthroposophic perspective considers a person's connections and relationships within communities rather than concentrating on them and the benefits of education (Lu & Jover, 2019). Therefore, the relevance of emotional and social intelligence in this context is stressed, and EE is further deployed to assist students

with their Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK studentships and life after graduation (Ilonen & Heinonen, 2018). Thus, the five primary levels of competence ingrained in affective learning (responding, valuing, organising, characterisation and receiving) are highlighted. These are all variations of emotional intelligence.

According to (Nabi, Linan & Fayolle, 2017) the key results of EE include changes in attitude, skills, entrepreneurial intention, knowledge, feasibility, socioeconomic effect, start-up and enterprise performance rates. Brentnall, Rodriguez & Culkin (2018) proposed the use of entrepreneurial attributes and qualities (entrepreneurship), a state of being (entrepreneurial), and the creation of an entrepreneurial climate and support structure (entrepreneurism) as the classifications for EE. Numerous metrics, such as affective, behavioural, cognitive, conative, and skill-based, can be used to assess these various forms of entrepreneurship education (Longva & Foss, 2018). Cognitive techniques that advance understanding of entrepreneurship, including enhancing understanding of the process of launching a company enterprise. Conative measurements entail assessing one's entrepreneurial efficacy.

Assessment of critical thinking abilities (social and emotional intelligence) and opportunity recognition is part of skill-based measures. Little research has been done on how students' specific learning strategies in entrepreneurship education affect their intention to become entrepreneurs (Bonesso, Bonesso, Gerli, Pizzi & Cortellazzo, 2018). Although student propensity for selfemployment predicts whether or not they will enroll in entrepreneurship courses, students seek to set themselves apart in the competitive job market with their unique skills, abilities, and attitudes. Due to this, students are becoming more interested in extracurricular activities that contrast with their prior schooling in a more formal context (Roulin & Bangerter, 2013), as blending extracurricular activities with entrepreneurship education reinforces the concepts covered in the classroom. When employed appropriately, extracurricular activities can significantly influence the learning process; according to earlier study (Cordea, 2014), this area of entrepreneurship is crucial.

In order to help students develop their civic participation, volunteering has been emphasised in entrepreneurship courses, particularly those with a social focus. Volunteering has many advantages, such as boosting confidence and personal development (Ratten & Usmanij, 2020). Santos, Neumeyer & Morris, (2018) students who experience novel settings may have a distinct learning outcome that varies from regular classroom situations. As a result, there is a symbiotic relationship that increases social wellness by allowing the community and students to study together. These instructional components may offer coping mechanisms that support the preservation of motivation and interest, raising aspirations for achievement and boosting entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Boldureanu et al., 2020). Moreover, EE is linked to entrepreneurial self-efficacy, which raises the possibility of achieving entrepreneurial intents since it denotes self-Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK assurance in one's capacity to carry out a variety of responsibilities and duties (Boldureanu et al., 2020).

Successful completion of any task is a function of intelligence. Intelligence is the ability to execute a task. To a non-specialist, it means inherent capacity, something the individual inherits from his or her parents, which determines mental growth. EI improves learning and problem-solving abilities; people with high EI

can establish a mood that enables them to perform better in complex activities. In support of this, (Checa & Fernández-Berrocal, 2015) indicated that participants with higher EI could complete complex tasks and did better than participants with lower EI. People who focus more on their feelings perform better on the emotional exercise. EI is the ability of people to effectively perceive emotions, use emotions to accurately promote thought, comprehend emotions, and manage their own and other people's emotions (Lopes, 2016; Puertas-Moler, ZuritaOrtega, Chacón-Cuberos, Castro-Sánchez, Ramírez-Granizo & González-Valero, 2020).

Mayer, Caruso and Salovey (2016) demonstrate that aptitude is the most accurate way to assess emotional intelligence. According to Gong, Chen and Wang (2019), EI is a collection of noncognitive talents and abilities that affect people's capacity to manage stress and environmental demands. Emotional intelligence broadly includes five areas, namely self-awareness, selfregulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills (Celik & Cetinkaya, 2022). Other research shows that soft skills play a role in 85% of career success and 15% of hard skills, namely the knowledge and technical skills students possess (Vasanthakumari, 2019). Social Intelligence (SI) can leverage basic social knowledge to determine other people's behaviour and cause changes in how people behave. However, it should be noted that social and emotional intelligence are two blood relatives that are mutually exclusive and in-exhaustive. As one of the soft skills units, EI has been identified to be the most significant. EI accelerate the ability to learn and solve dimensions of problems. Persons with higher EI can generate a mood that enables them to perform better on complex cognitive tasks. In support of this, (Checa & Fernández-Berrocal, 2015) indicated that participants with higher EI quickly solve more cognitive tasks than those with a lower EI. The ability to execute collaboration and coordination in social interactions is known as social intelligence. As a result, it offers information that is easy to understand about a strategy for motivating people to achieve their own life goals. Social awareness and social talent are the classifications of SI (Ali et al., 2019).

Social intelligence (SI) plays a crucial role in the lives of individuals, as it helps them understand other persons and characteristics, rationalise their motives and interpret their emotions and expressions. SI is very useful in solving problems in our social lives, tackling various social tasks, and developing healthy cooperation with others. It is the key element that makes people succeed Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK (Raj & Komalavalli, 2022). SI develops through human experience and societal learning based on successes and mistakes. It is commonly called tact, common sense, or street smarts. Socially competent people learn how to play a variety of social roles. They're also well-versed in the "norms," or unwritten rules that govern social interaction. In other words, they "know how to play the game" in social situations. As a result, they are mature and prudent in social situations. With these, we cannot avoid the concept of social intelligence (Mehta, 2021).

Social intelligence refers to the ability to understand and manage others and display wise behaviour in interaction with others. Some components of social intelligence include perceptual, analyticalcognitive, and behavioural components. This can be perceived as the ability to understand and rein in one's emotions and feelings to help with intellectual activities, decision-making, and communication (Karimi & Ataei, 2023). Social intelligence, or social skills, refers to how well people are aware of and interact with each other in different contexts, as it enables employees to avoid conflict, manage expectations, and

communicate successfully. Learning social skills and how to improve them can help an individual have better workplace relationships and a healthy work environment (Benkirane & Benazzi, 2024). Therefore, people with high social intelligence are more likely to handle stress, be self-confident, and feel supported, making them more prone to entrepreneurial intentions. The ability to successfully navigate life is highly dependent on social intelligence because it benefits both individuals and society. This affects the relationships people build with partners, children, and friends and their career development (Tamasila et al., 2024).

This kind of intelligence means that one is aware of the thoughts and feelings of others, even if they do not share or describe them explicitly. Essential traits characterising socially intelligent people include effective listening and communication, respecting their impression of others, and consciously avoiding arguments (Ordun et al., 2021). Four components of SI can be inferred: social awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, and relationship management. Self-awareness is the ability to understand one's abilities, thoughts, and feelings and self-involvement in how one responds to others. Self-regulation or self-management refers to how an individual applies self-awareness to cope with challenging situations, likening to an internal decision-making process. The significance of social intelligence has been relayed empirically as (Obilor & Ikpa, 2020) investigated social intelligence and academic achievement. The characteristics of the inquiry are correlational research design, 800 finite population, 240 sample size leveraging simple random sampling technique, and the reliability coefficient yielded 0.81. Descriptive statistics was employed in the data analysis while the null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significance level. Self-awareness, self-motivation, and empathy were found correlated with students' academic performance of students were significantly found correlated.

Mehta (2021) studied social intelligence concerning respondents' academic successes at India's Udaipur district. The study's attributes are 130 respondents were recruited out of which 103 showed voluntary participation, non-experimental quantitative surveys and interviews. Count, percentage, mean, standard deviation, one-sample t-test, and correlation were utilised as tools and tests. It was revealed that socially intelligent people could handle challenges better and perform better than those whose EQ was judged to be low. Also, in a study conducted by (Karimi & Ataei, 2023) on agricultural students' entrepreneurial skills mediated by social and emotional intelligence, with a sample size of 269 out of 893 and 0.92 reliability coefficient. The entrepreneurship ecosystem, SI, and EI positively influenced the students' entrepreneurial skills.

In order to accommodate students' interests and abilities, non-academic activities are a variety of organized activities that help students become more connected and involved in their groups and build soft and social skills that support wellbeing (Mishra & Aithal, 2023). Also, students may engage in school-approved non-academic activities (EAs) beyond of the normal school day. Higher academic accomplishment is one of the many advantages of EA participation that have been linked to students. Sports, clubs, religious organisations, and fine arts programmes are a few examples (Morris, 2019). Other examples of extracurricular activities include tutoring or counselling, fundraising, arts, school clubs, student government, school publications), community (neighbourhood involvement, community youth

and organisations, Enactus), and religious (youth group, participating in services. Mishra & Aithal, (2023) listed events, voluntary work, and leadership roles in different committees as part of the EAs.

This study is based on the theories supporting the core constructs of the investigation. Different theoretical (self-determination, human capital and entrepreneurial self-efficacy) backings contend that EE is positively associated with students' entrepreneurial intentions due to its efficacies in equipping students with the necessary knowledge and skills and spurring them to pursue their entrepreneurial careers. However, the current study will use human capital theory to emphasise entrepreneurship. This theory suggests that individuals can enhance their entrepreneurial abilities and potential through education and training (Boldureanu et al., 2020). EE aims to develop the human capital of aspiring entrepreneurs by providing them with the necessary skills and knowledge.

Emotional intelligence (EI) is the understanding, evaluation, and management of personal and other feelings with the goal of problem-solving and learning. Thus, the ability-based emotional intelligence paradigm combines four essential emotional competencies created by Mayer et al. (2016). The ability to appropriately perceive and understand personal and other people's emotions is the first skill, which is the practice of social adaptation. The second competency promotes achieving goals by managing one's own and other people's emotional states. The third competency is using one's emotions to solve problems healthily. The fourth competency calls for emotional self-regulation to maintain emotional and intellectual development over time. Over the years, research and education have recognised this approach to emotional intelligence (EI) (Chakrabarti & Chatterjea, 2018; Zhoc et al., 2018).

Additionally, emotional contagion theory posits that students are greatly influenced by their mentors' traits and emotional displays, i.e., the lecturers. Hence, instructors who engage in emotional intelligence (EI) can inspire students to achieve their full potential. Additionally, the entity theory of intelligence holds that intelligence is stable and fixed as it enhances negativity and discourages learning. In contrast, the incremental intelligence theory indicates that intelligence can be changed and increased by enhancing positive emotions that support staff in fostering learning outcomes (Shafait, Khan, Muhammad, Bilan & Oláh, 2021). Therefore, this study is a conscious attempt in exploring how Ekiti State's entrepreneurship education may be advanced through social and emotional intelligence.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. A self-constructed instrument was employed to obtain adequate information from the population (male and female 300 and 400-level entrepreneurship students in Ekiti State Tertiary Institutions). Strategically, a non-probability sampling technique (multi-stage) was used to sample the higher institutions and the entrepreneurship students, as it suits the study's nature. Deliberately, 100-level and 200-level students were excluded due to their limited knowledge of entrepreneurship. Secondary and primary data constituted the sources of data for the study. The finite population (100) for the entrepreneurship students in Ekiti State University (71) and Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology Ikere (29). Only 78 showed voluntary participation, 29 BOUESTI, and 49 EKSU. The study will adopt a non-probability sampling technique (multi-stage) to sample out respondents for the study, as it suits the study's nature.

1st Stage: Purposive sampling of Ekiti State in Nigeria. 2nd Stage: Simple random sampling of two senatorial districts in Ekiti State (Ekiti Central Senatorial District and Ekiti Southern Senatorial District). 3rd Stage: Purposive sampling of one Local Government area from the selected senatorial districts (two Local Government Areas) (Ikere and Ado). 4th Stage: Stratified random sampling of one town each in the selected Local Government Areas (Ikere and Ado). 5th Stage: Purposive sampling of one tertiary institution from the selected two towns (Ekiti State University Ado-Ekiti and Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology Ikere-Ekiti). The data collection was done with the help of research assistants. The researcher trained the research assistants on the proper and effective instrument administration. Descriptive statistics was employed to analyse the primary data collected, leveraging the statistical package for social Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK sciences (SPSS). Ethical approval was given by BOUESTI's University Research and Training Committee after the requirements had been fulfilled.

A decision rule was set to accept or reject the mean score. This was based on

$$\frac{N5 + N4 + N3 + N2 + N1}{\frac{5}{15} \frac{5}{5}}$$

=3; Where SA=5, A=4, U=3, D=2 and, SD=1.

A decision rule of 3 mean cut-off points was set, and this means that any questionnaire statement with more than three mean scores is accepted while the statement with less than the mean cut-off score is rejected. The mean is a statistical tool used to measure the research questions.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics

Variables	Frequency	Valid Percentage
Age:		
16-19years	3	3.8
20-23years	37	47.4
24-27years	20	25.6
28-31years	18	23.1
32years and above Total	-	-
	78	100.0
Gender:		
Male	33	42.3
Female	45	57.7
Total	78	100.0
Family Size:		

1	2	2.6
2	1	1.3
3	11	14.1 20.5
4	16 23 25	29.5
5	78	32.1
6 and above		100
Total		
Religion:		
Christianity	67	85.9
Islam	11	14.1
Others (specify)	-	-
Total	78	100.0

Ethnicity:		
Yoruba	62	79.5
Igbo	9	11.5
Hausa	4	5.1 3.8
Others	3	100.0
Total	78	
Marital Status:		
Married	11	14.1
Single	67	85.9
Total	78	100.0
Level of Study:		
100 level	-	-
200 Level	-	-
300 Level	34	43.6
400 level Total	44	56.4
	78	100.0
Most Impactful Course:		

Research Methodology	7	8.97
Practical Acquisition	5	6.41 5.13 1.28
Measuring Organisational Success	4	2.56
Start-up Funding	1	39.74
Project Management	2	12.82
Customer Relationship Management	31	7.69
Book Keeping	10	6.41
Element of Economics	6	
Leadership and Corporate Governance	5	3.85
Business Mathematics	3	5.13
Family Business and Succession Planning	4	100
Total	78	

Source: Research’s Database, (2025).

Table 1, the dataset comprehensively represents the socio-demographic characteristics of the study's respondents. There are diverse age group representations between 16 and 31 with varying frequencies and valid percentages, while most individuals aged between 20 and 23. The sample consisted of 33 (42.3%) male and 45 (57.7%) female participants, indicating a rare predominance of females. There is a concord between this finding and the submission of (Babu et al., 2020).

25 (32.1%) of the respondents accounted for a larger family size: six family members and above. This was followed serially by 23 (29.5%), 16 (20.5%), 11 (14.1%), 2 (2.6%) and 1 (1.3%) with corresponding family sizes (5, 4, 3, 1 and 2) respectively. The religious composition consisted of 67 (85.9%) adherents of Christianity and 11 (28%) followers of Islamic beliefs. In the marital Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK attribute of the respondents, 67(85.9%) were classified as single, and 11 (22%) were married. Furthermore, 56.4% of the respondents are in the 400 level, representing 44, while the remaining are in the 300 level of their BSc programme (Entrepreneurship). The last monthly allowance spent by the respondents (students) is ₦5,000, and the highest is ₦130,000. This shows the respondents' family financial capacity as the financial strength of families differs. Also, this range aligns with the country's current economic realities.

Figure 1: Ethnicity Distribution of the Respondents

Source: Researchers' Database, (2025).

The ethnic composition of the sample was diverse, with 62 (79.5%) identifying as Yoruba, 9 (11.5%) as Igbo, 4 (5.1%) as Hausa, and the remaining 3 (3.8%) representing other ethnic groups schooling in the study area (Ekiti State, Nigeria).

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Figure 2: Respondents' Distribution of the Most Impactful Course

Source: Researchers' Database, (2025).

Majority of the students found customer relationship management as the most impactful course since 100 level up till the moment (300 and 400 level). In reality, it shows the connection between SI and EI in relation to managing customers.

Table 2: Efficacy of Emotional Intelligence in Promoting Extracurricular Activities among Entrepreneurship Students

S/N	Statement	Mean	Std.dev	Skewness	Remark
1	I can clearly identify the reasons for my feelings toward extracurricular activities.	3.50	1.45	-0.856	Accept
2	I have a good understanding of my emotions when excelling in sporting activities.	3.53	1.52	-0.747	Accept
3	I understand what I feel in a bad situation	3.69	1.24	-0.852	Accept
4	I can indicate if I am happy while participating in debates	3.67	1.26	-0.632	Accept
5	I can distinguish my colleagues' emotions from their behaviour in extracurricular activities	3.81	1.23	-1.090	Accept
6	I have sensitive feelings and emotions of others in religious activities	3.73	1.20	-1.116	Accept
7	I motivate myself in community activities	3.86	1.12	-0.895	Accept
8	I can control my temper in difficult situations	3.85	1.15	-0.947	Accept
9	I have reasonable control over managing self-aggression	3.91	1.11	-0.938	Accept
10	I have reasonable control over managing irresponsible behaviour in extracurricular activities	3.83	1.25	-1.100	Accept
11	I can quickly adapt to people's peculiarity in order to achieve my goals	3.73	1.35	-1.034	Accept
12	My mood swing helps me perform better in activities	3.68	1.20	-0.737	Accept

13	I can manage other people's emotion	3.71	1.20	-0.712	Accept
14	I used to feel other people's pain	3.74	1.18	-0.901	Accept
15	There is self-motivation to overcome bad moments.	3.92	1.27	-1.348	Accept
16	I can regulate myself when I am under the influence.	3.92	1.16	-1.180	Accept
17	There is a self-awareness about my emotions	3.91	1.18	-1.103	Accept
18	My mood flexibility assists me in solving problems	3.88	1.29	-1.198	Accept

Source: Researchers' Database, (2025).

From the table 2 above, all the statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14,15, 16, 17 and 18 have mean scores of 3.50, 3.53, 3.69, 3.67, 3.81, 3.73, 3.86, 3.85, 3.91, 3.83, 3.73, 3.68, 3.71, 3.74, 3.92, 3.92, 3.91 and 3.88 respectively which are above the mean cut off point of 3, indicating that the statements are accepted. None of the statements rejected regarding the efficacy of emotional intelligence in promoting extracurricular activities among entrepreneurship students since all the statements have a lower mean score than the mean score cut-off (3). The study reveals that emotional intelligence has more substantial efficacy on extracurricular activities (sport, debate, religious activities, community activities and other

non-academic affairs) within the spectrum of good sense of feelings, a better understanding of self-emotions, self-feeling, happy mood, understanding and managing other people's feelings and emotions, self-motivation, temper control, adaptation, mood swing, empathy, self-motivation, self-regulation, self-awareness and flexibility in their engagement with self and others.

These findings empirically align with previous works on measuring emotional intelligence indices. The results of (García-Sancho et al., 2014; Kopera et al., 2015) supported the findings on selfregulation as an EI attribute that helps people who possess it manage aggression and irresponsible behaviour. Ford & Tamir (2012) stressed the importance of adaptation as an integral part of EI in assisting them to adapt to other people's peculiarity. It was emphatically relayed by (Checa & Fernández-Berrocal, 2015) that persons with higher EI can sometimes generate different moods to cope with the current situation and perform better than others with low or no emotional intelligence. (Lopes, 2016; Puertas-Moler, Zurita-Ortega, Chacón-Cuberos, Castro-Sánchez, Ramírez-Granizo & González-Valero, 2020) inquired into emotional intelligence in organisations and emotional intelligence in the field of education respectively. They found that people with Ei can manage self and other peoples' emotions.

Based on the analysis and interpretation, the current study agrees with this. Furthermore, the categorisation of EI by (Celik & Cetinkaya, 2022) into areas of empathy, motivation, selfregulation and self-awareness further aligns the study's results with existing body of knowledge. (Checa & Fernández-Berrocal, 2015) found that the flexibility of people with high EI gives them an edge in solving complex tasks than their counterparts with lower EI. This concords with the current study, as it has enabled them to solve problems in their extracurricular activities.

Negative skewness (left-skewed) indicates the tail is longer on the left side, indicating more data points are concentrated on the higher end. Positive skewness (right-skewed) indicates the tail is longer on the right side, indicating more data points are concentrated on the lower end. A skewness value between -0.5 and 0.5 is approximately symmetric, while values outside this range indicate increasing asymmetry.

Generally, all the values are skewed in the negative direction, which means the data distributions are left-skewed, i.e. they tend towards the higher end of agree and strongly agree. The skewness is analysed in the category of mild negative skewness and high negative skewness. The statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 12, 13 and 14 with the corresponding -0.856, -0.747, -0.852, -0.632, -0.895, 0.947, -0.938, -0.737, -0.712, and -0.901 respectively indicate moderate negative skewness. This implies that the statements are moderately balanced but rarely lean towards higher values. Conclusively, statements 5, 6, 10, 11, 15, 16, 17, and 18, with the corresponding values -1.090, 1.116, -1.100 and -1.348, -1.180, -1.103 and -1.198, respectively, show higher positives since they are skewed in the upper range. By implication, the consistency of the negative skewness indicates that respondents are positive about self-control, emotional awareness, and empathy in nonacademic activities.

Table 3: Efficacy of Social Intelligence in Enhancing Academic Activities among Entrepreneurship Students

S/N	Statement	Mean	Std.dev	Skewness	Remark
19	I have been able to create bonds with my colleagues in the university for improved reading habit	3.87	1.46	-1.229	Accept

20	I can co-exist in a larger class to solve academic problems	3.76	1.36	-0.943	Accept
21	I understand why people behave the way they behave	3.72	1.28	-1.020	Accept
22	I can perform in any role given to play at the University	3.74	1.26	-0.847	Accept
23	Social awareness of different humans with different attitudes helps me to avoid conflict with fellow students	3.86	1.35	-1.213	Accept
24	My expectations of fellow students are not high	3.68	1.33	-0.869	Accept
25	I have been communicating effectively with fellow students	3.77	1.30	-1.090	Accept
26	I have a good working relationship with my colleagues at the University	3.92	1.29	-1.204	Accept
27	I am good at managing stress	4.10	1.16	-1.597	Accept
28	I have self-confidence in my ability to excel in academics	4.03	1.22	-1.427	Accept
29	I have practical listening skills, which have been helping in my curricular activities	3.91	1.02	-1.166	Accept
30	I avoid arguments as much as possible	4.04	1.32	-1.417	Accept
31	I can predict fellow students' following behaviour based on previous knowledge.	3.85	1.33	-1.241	Accept
32	I have empathy for students battling with academic challenges	3.92	1.27	-1.151	Accept

Source: Researchers' Database, (2025).

From table 3 above, all the statements 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, and 32 have mean scores of 3.87, 3.76, 3.72, 3.74, 3.86, 3.68, 3.77, 3.92, 4.10, 4.03, 3.91, 4.04, 3.85 and 3.92 respectively which are above the mean cut off point of 3, indicating that the statements are accepted. None of the statements is rejected since the mean scores exceeded the mean cut-off (3) concerning the efficacy of social intelligence in enhancing curricular activities among entrepreneurship students. The study found that social intelligence has greater efficacy on curricular activities within the space of bonding with other colleagues for excellent academic activities, co-existence, performing in any given role, social awareness, no or moderate expectation, effective communication, working relationship, stress management, practical listening skills, avoiding arguments, behaviour prediction and empathy. These findings empirically concur with past investigations on the measuring factors of social intelligence. The inquiry (Ross, 2015) supported the findings on social bonds as an SI trait that helps individuals create bonds and co-exist with others in a community. Social bond-SI is viewed as something that is learnable and not a talent. (Mehta, 2021) found that socially competent people can perform different social roles.

Also, the findings corroborate the stand of (Benkirane & Benazzi, 2024) on social awareness, which gives socially intelligent people the ability to avoid conflict, manage expectations, and communicate successfully. Most importantly, social awareness assists in building healthy working relationships. The investigation (Raj & Komalavalli, 2022), which captured the understanding of other people's behaviour as a unit of SI, is consistent with the findings in this section. It enables the respondent to understand why people behave

the way they behave. Putting no or moderate expectations on others is a key trait of SI; the socially intelligent places little or no expectation on others. There is no disagreement between the current study and the effort (Benkirane & Benazzi, 2024). The pieces of literature from (Benkirane and Benazzi, 2024; Ordun et al., 2021) indicated a high level of effective communication among socially intelligent people. This aligns with the revelation of the current study.

(Tamasila et al., 2024), ability to manage stress is another benefit of possessing SI; the respondents can manage the associated stress of academic work. Thus, there is a correlation between this stand and the revelation of this study. People with high SI possess another unique trait of practical listening skills, as indicated by (Ordun et al., 2021). This also gives them an edge in the temperament of engaging in an argument. There is an opportunity for socially intelligent people to develop empathy for others (Tamasila et al., 2024); this is more useful for students as they face daily challenges from themselves and others.

Generally, all the values skewed to a negative direction ranging from the least value -.0847 to the highest -1.597, which means the data is left-skewed, i.e. they tend towards the higher end of agree Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK and strongly agree. The skewness is analysed in the category of mild negative skewness and high negative skewness. Statements 20, 22 and 24, corresponding to -0.943, -0.847, and -0.869, respectively, indicate moderate negative skewness. This implies that the statements are moderately balanced but rarely lean towards higher values. Furthermore, statements 19, 21, 23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31 and 32 with the corresponding values -1.229, -1.020, -1.213, -1.090, -1.204, -1.597, 1.427, -1.166, -1.417, -1.241 and -1.151 respectively show higher positive skewness since they are skewed in the upper range. By implication, the consistency of the negative skewness indicates that respondents are optimistic about the elements of social intelligence measured in academic activities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that EI is highly effective in promoting extracurricular activities. Also, SI influences curricular activities by enhancing bonding with other colleagues, promoting excellent academic activities, and performing in any given role. Therefore, it is recommended that students possess more EI and SI for overall performance and managing themselves and others.

Practical Implications

The results have implications for enhancing students' engagement in both academic and nonacademic activities, even beyond the scope of entrepreneurship education. This would later positively affect their lives during and after school as employers of labour, employees and parents/guardians. Above all, it is a mechanism to boost positive relationships.

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